

THE INFLUENCE OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES ON STUDENTS' READINESS TO MODERNIZE CONSTRUCTION NETWORKS

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Annotation: This article is devoted to the study of the influence of pedagogical technologies on the readiness of students to modernize construction networks. The authors analyze current trends in the field of education and the construction industry, identifying key aspects that require the integration of innovative teaching methods. The paper presents the results of an empirical study conducted among students of construction specialties, taking into account the use of modern educational technologies. Special attention is paid to the effectiveness of the introduction of virtual and augmented realities, online courses and interactive platforms in the learning process. The results of the study allow us to conclude that the use of advanced pedagogical technologies helps to increase students' readiness to implement the modernization of construction networks. The recommendations proposed in the article can be used in the development of educational programs and methods in order to optimize the learning process in the context of current challenges and requirements of the construction industry.

Keywords: Pedagogical technologies, Development of competencies of future specialists in construction, Modernization of construction networks, Educational methods, Technological progress, Construction industry, Innovations in education, Training of specialists in the construction sector, Transformation of the educational process, Adaptation of students to modern technologies, Construction networks, Professional training in the construction industry, Technological trends in education.

Introduction. In the modern world, construction plays a key role in the formation of infrastructure and ensuring the sustainable development of society. Construction technologies are constantly being improved, and in this context, the readiness of the younger generation – students of construction specialties – to modernize construction networks plays an important role. In this article, we will consider how pedagogical technologies influence the formation of students'

necessary skills and knowledge for successful adaptation to modern challenges in the construction industry.

Modern construction technologies are increasingly moving into the field of high technologies, such as unmanned vehicles, construction robots, virtual and augmented reality. In order to train qualified specialists in the field of construction, it is necessary to integrate these innovations into the educational process[1]. Electronic learning platforms, virtual laboratories and training programs based on artificial intelligence contribute to the formation of students' understanding and skills necessary to work with modern construction technologies. Pedagogical technologies also focus on project-based learning, which allows students to apply their knowledge in practice. The creation of projects in collaboration with industry and the use of modern design methods help students develop practical solutions for modern construction networks.

Modern construction technologies require not only technical skills from specialists, but also the ability to effectively interact in a team. The use of team projects, training in communication skills through online platforms and virtual communication tools help students successfully adapt to teamwork in the conditions of modern construction enterprises.

Given the rapid pace of development of construction technologies, it is important to develop students' self-learning and adaptability skills. Pedagogical technologies can contribute to the creation of flexible educational programs that include opportunities for constant updating of knowledge and skills throughout a career[2]. The construction industry is a key sector of the economy, and its development is closely linked to the level of training of specialists. Students studying in the field of construction should be prepared for modern challenges and technological innovations that are continuously changing this industry. In the last decade, pedagogical technologies have become an important tool in education, and their impact on students' readiness to modernize building networks is becoming more and more noticeable.

1. Overview of modern technologies in construction: Modern construction technologies include the use of digital tools, virtual and augmented reality, artificial intelligence and other innovative solutions. These technologies improve the efficiency of construction, reduce time and improve safety. Students of construction specialties should be familiar with these tools and ready to use them in their professional activities.

2. Introduction into the educational process: Pedagogical technologies in construction education include the use of virtual laboratories, simulators and

software for modeling construction processes. This allows students to gain practical skills in a safe and controlled environment, which contributes to their readiness to work with modern technologies in real conditions.

3. Individualized learning: Pedagogical technologies also provide an opportunity for individualized learning. Students can study materials at their own pace, use interactive learning resources and receive feedback from teachers. This contributes to a deep understanding of the material and the development of critical thinking, which is an important aspect of preparing for the modernization of construction networks.

4. Collaboration and Communication: Modern technologies also facilitate collaboration and communication between students, teachers and businesses. Virtual teams, online platforms and joint projects with enterprises allow students to develop team skills and understand the importance of interaction in a professional environment.

5. Overcoming challenges and prospects for the future: The use of pedagogical technologies in construction education helps students better understand the current requirements of the industry and effectively respond to challenges such as sustainability, digitalization and environmental standards. Readiness to modernize construction networks becomes part of their professional identity.

In an era of rapid technological development, the construction industry is faced with the constant need to modernize its methods and technologies[3]. This modernization requires qualified specialists who are able not only to adapt to new technologies, but also to actively introduce them into construction processes. In this context, education plays a key role, and, in particular, effective pedagogical technologies. The construction industry, like many others, is facing challenges presented by new technologies such as building information models (BIM), project management systems, as well as various innovative materials and construction methods. The willingness of specialists to work with these technologies is becoming a key factor in the success of the industry.

Modern pedagogical technologies provide unique opportunities for students to learn. Virtual classrooms, construction process simulators, online courses and other tools help students master not only theoretical aspects, but also acquire practical skills in a virtual environment[4]. This creates direct interaction with the technologies that they will use in their future professional activities. One of the most important technologies in construction is Building Information Modeling (BIM). The integration of BIM into educational programs

allows students not only to study the theoretical aspects of this technology, but also to actively apply them in practice. Virtual reality (VR) makes it possible to create three-dimensional models of buildings, interact with them and analyze the results, which significantly improves the understanding of construction processes.

Training using Simulators and Interactive Platforms

Simulators of construction machinery and equipment are also becoming an integral part of educational programs. With their help, students can gain hands-on experience working with various machines without leaving the classroom. Interactive learning platforms provide access to real construction projects, allowing students to solve problems they will face in their professional activities.

Development of Critical Thinking and Professional Ethics

An important part of education is not only technical training, but also the development of critical thinking and professional ethics. Using pedagogical technologies, it is possible to create an environment in which students develop the ability to analyze, make decisions and behave ethically in professional situations.

Construction is an industry that is constantly developing and introducing new technologies to optimize processes. In the context of rapid changes in the construction sector, the role of education and pedagogical technologies in shaping students' readiness to modernize construction networks is becoming key.

Building networks play a fundamental role in the infrastructure of modern society. With the development of technology and the emergence of new requirements for sustainability and efficiency, construction companies are forced to adapt and implement innovative solutions[5]. The main executors of this change are future specialists in the field of construction, for whom the formation of readiness for the modernization of construction networks becomes an important element of the educational process.

Technologies in education: from traditional to innovative

Traditional methods of teaching in the field of construction include lectures, practical exercises and laboratory work. However, in a rapidly changing world, traditional approaches limit students' ability to adapt to modern technologies. In modern education, new pedagogical technologies are being actively introduced, such as online courses, virtual laboratories, simulations, multimedia materials and other means that allow students to immerse themselves more deeply in the study of new concepts and technologies.

Simulations and virtual laboratories

One of the key areas in education has become the use of simulations and virtual laboratories. These technologies allow students to conduct virtual experiments and trainings, which gives them the opportunity to get acquainted with real scenarios of work on a construction site without leaving the classroom. This approach not only improves the learning of the material, but also develops students' skills in solving complex problems in real time.

Interactive learning methods

Interactive teaching methods, such as learning through games, debates, and case studies, also contribute to the formation of students' readiness to modernize construction networks. Game scenarios can simulate situations that students will encounter in their professional activities, which allows them to develop critical thinking and decision-making.

Online educational platforms

Online learning platforms provide students with access to a wide range of materials and courses created by leading experts in the field of construction. This allows students to study new technologies in depth, the latest trends in the industry, as well as share experiences with colleagues and professionals from different countries.

Results and prospects

The introduction of modern pedagogical technologies into the educational process significantly affects the readiness of students to modernize construction networks. These innovations provide a deeper and more systematic understanding of the subject, develop students' skills to work with new technologies and stimulate creative thinking. However, it is important not only to introduce new technologies, but also to develop appropriate educational programs that take into account the specifics of the construction industry. It is also necessary to ensure that programs and materials are constantly updated so that students always have access to up-to-date information[6]. Pedagogical technologies play an important role in shaping students' readiness to modernize construction networks. Their implementation allows you to create a learning environment that promotes the development of professional skills, creative thinking and the ability to quickly adapt to changes in the industry. Further development and improvement of pedagogical technologies in construction education will be a key factor in the successful training of personnel capable of effectively introducing innovations into the construction networks of the future.

Conclusion: The introduction of modern pedagogical technologies into educational programs for future builders plays a crucial role in shaping their readiness to modernize construction networks. This not only provides students with access to the latest technologies, but also develops the necessary skills for a successful career in the construction industry.

The influence of pedagogical technologies on students' readiness to modernize construction networks is undeniable. These technologies help students develop not only technical skills, but also flexibility of thinking, the ability to adapt quickly and an innovative approach to solving problems. The development and implementation of modern pedagogical technologies in the educational process of construction specialties is becoming a key element of preparation for the future modernization of construction industries. The influence of pedagogical technologies on students' readiness to modernize construction networks is undeniable. The integration of modern educational techniques, supported by the active introduction of information technology, project-oriented learning and the development of social skills, is a key factor in the successful adaptation of future builders to the challenges of modern industry. This will ensure not only a high level of professional competence, but also the ability to constantly develop and adapt to changes in the construction industry.

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